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Feasibility of conductive embroidered threads for I²C sensors in microcontroller-based wearable electronics

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In recent years, the importance of flexible and textile electronics in the field of wearable devices has continuously increased, as they are expected to replace conventional wires that exhibit limited resistance to the mechanical stress occurring in on-body applications. Wearable Health Devices (WHDs) can provide physiological information about various body parts and employ distributed sensor networks. Among the sensors typically integrated within WHDs, those based on the I²C communication protocol are very common and exploit signals transmitted at frequencies up to hundreds of kilohertz. Therefore, robust communication is required to guarantee a proper transmission of the signal at those frequencies. In this context, we have realized embroidered conductive threads exhibiting a lower resistance, appositely designed to replace conventional wires in a microcontroller-based wearable device employing I²C sensors. A commercial conductive thread (silver coated polyamide) was used to embroider the conductive lines on to cotton fabric. Preliminary measurements were performed to characterize the response of these materials to signals typically operated within the I²C communication protocol at different path lengths. Resistive measurements have also been performed to simulate different environmental conditions, that is, temperature, the effect of sweating, and repeated washing cycles, also apply mechanical stress, i.e., twisting, with promising results that validate our conductive paths for digital signal communication.

Figure 1: (a) An illustration of the experimental set up: the microcontroller shares SDA and SCL signals to I²C device by two separate I²C ports using commercial copper (I) and embroidered (II) wires, acquiring signals present in both lines with oscilloscope. (b) Schematic representation of step-by-step process of embedding conductive yarns into textile through embroidery technique.

References

- [1] S. V. Iyer, J. George, S. Sathiyamoorthy, R. Palanisamy, A. Majumdar, and P. Veluswamy, "Pertinence of Textile-Based Energy Harvesting System for Biomedical Applications," *Journal of Nanomaterials*, vol. 2022, p. e7921479, Aug. 2022.
- [2] M. Radouchova, S. Suchy, and T. Blecha, "Embroidered Flexible Elastic Textile Antenna as Strain Sensor," in *2022 45th International Spring Seminar on Electronics Technology (ISSE)*, May 2022, pp. 1–6.
- [3] J. Heikenfeld et al., "Wearable sensors: modalities, challenges, and prospects," *Lab on a Chip*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 217–248, 2018.
- [4] J. L. Gbur and J. J. Lewandowski, "Fatigue and fracture of wires and cables for biomedical applications," *International Materials Reviews*, May 2016.
- [5] B. J. Benini, "Tension and Flex Fatigue Behavior of Small Diameter Wires for Biomedical Applications," Case Western Reserve University, 2010.
- [6] "Special conductive thread by AMANN: Silver-tech+." <https://www.amann.com/products/product/silver-tech-plus/> (accessed Oct. 10, 2022).
- [7] J. T. F. Ding, X. Tao, W. M. Au, and L. Li, "Temperature effect on the conductivity of knitted fabrics embedded with conducting yarns," *Textile Research Journal*, Apr. 2014.
- [8] "Testing in artificial sweat – Is less more? Comparison of metal release in two different artificial sweat solutions," *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, vol. 81, pp. 381–386, Nov. 2016.
- [9] "Special conductive thread by AMANN: Silver-tech+." <https://www.amann.com/products/product/silver-tech-plus/> (accessed Oct. 26, 2022).
- [10] J. Allen, "Photoplethysmography and its application in clinical physiological measurement," *Physiol. Meas.*, vol. 28, no. 3, p. R1, Feb. 2007, doi: 10.1088/0967-3334/28/3/R01.
- [11] S. Afroj, S. Tan, A. M. Abdelkader, K. S. Novoselov, and N. Karim, "Highly Conductive, Scalable, and Machine Washable Graphene-Based E-Textiles for Multifunctional Wearable Electronic Applications," *Advanced Functional Materials*, vol. 30, no. 23, p. 2000293, Jun. 2020.
- [12] S. Rotzler and M. Schneider-Ramelow, "Washability of E-Textiles: Failure Modes and Influences on Washing Reliability," *Textiles*, vol. 1, no. 1, Art. no. 1, Jun. 2021.
- [13] S. Sharma, "Review on CAN based Intercommunication between Microcontrollers," vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 137–140, 2015.

